

ON MODLE-II DELAMINATION FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF MULTI-DIRECTIONAL INTERFACE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATE

Jun Xiao and Shun-lin Li
(Nanjing Aeronautical Institute, Nanjing, P.R.China)

ABSTRACT

A method to measure modle-II delamination fracture toughness of multi-directional interface in composite laminate is put forward with end notch flexure specimen, with which the fracture toughness of interface ($G(0/\theta)$) in aramid/epoxy composite laminate is measured in this work.

INTRODUCTION

The study on delamination fracture is one of important branches in mechanics of composite materials. It is on two main points: analyzing on interlaminar stresses and deterring of delamination parameters and failure criteria. For the later, there are two methods: material strength method and fracture mechanics method. Many works have been done on material strength. 1-3 In recent years, delamination studies have been focused on the fracture mechanics 4-7. In 1985, Rusell and Street put forward a method to measure modle-II delamination fracture toughness of unidirectional composite with end notch flexure (ENF for short) specimen⁶. In 1986, Carlsson made a detail discussion on ENF method, including specimen size, stability of crack growth and in fluence of friction between crack surfaces⁷. The delamination fracture toughness of unidirectional composite has become one of elementary properties of the composite, more and more attention has been paid to it.

The composite is used usually in the form of multi-directional laminate to meet different requirements. There are many differences between multi-directional interface and unidirectional interface in micro-structure, macro-properties and delamination mechanisim^{2,3,8}. Thus it is important to study delamination fracture of multi-directional laminate both in theory and in engineering applications.

Based on laminated beam theory, the formula of ENF methed with multi-directional laminated beam is derived in this paper. The modle-II delamination fracture toughness of interface ($G(0/\theta)$) in aramid/epoxy composite laminate is measured. The result shown that, $G(0/\theta)$ the modle-II fracture toughness of interface ($G(0/\theta)$), differs from that of unidirectional interface and varies with ply-anage θ .

THE ENF METHOD FOR MEASURING FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF MULTI-DIRECTIONAL INTERFACE

1. Test Method and Calculation Formulas

The analyzed modle, as shown in Fig.1 is a three-point flexure laminated beam with stacking sequence $[0_m/\theta]_s$. An artificial crack at the right end divides section AB of the beam into two sub-beams in the upper interface ($0/\theta$). Because these beams are laminated beams with finite width, the free edge effect will arise and residual stress is produced when working temperature is different from curing temperature.

Therefore a new formula is needed to calculate the fracture toughness of multi-directional interface. The stability of crack growth should be discussed on the new model.

First, the energy release rate produced by applied load is considered. Because of the free edge effect there are τ_{yz} and σ_z besides τ_{xz} in specimen. The delamination of fracture of the model composes of three elementary fractures. According to the results calculated with the method proposed in the Reference⁹, in the case of $m=5$, τ_{yz} in the laminated beam [05/45]_s is the maximum, but it is only 1.9 percent of τ_{xz} ; σ_z in upper interface is compressed stress. It is obvious that delamination is caused mainly by model-II fracture. Since the interlaminar stresses produced by the free edge effect are very small and they affect only in a local region near the free edge, the energy release rate can be calculated by the beam theory.

Fig. 1 ENF specimen

Based on Russell's theory, the compliance of the beam is

$$C = \frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{\delta_{AB} + \delta_{BC} + \delta_{CD}}{2P} \quad (1)$$

The relative displacement δ_{CD} and δ_{BC} given by the beam theory are as follows:

$$\delta_{CD} = \frac{Pl^3}{6EJ} + \mu \frac{Pl}{2\bar{G}A}$$

$$\delta_{BC} = \frac{2l^3 - 3al^2 + a^3}{12EJ} + \mu \frac{P(1-a)}{2\bar{G}A} \quad (2)$$

where EJ and $\bar{G}A$ are stiffness for flexure and shear respectively, μ is a beam coefficient.

For δ_{AB} , a supposition is made that the slopes of both the beam and sub-beams are equal at point B. Considering that the bending deflection of sub-beam's coordinate at point A, δ_{AB} can be got by the cantilever beam theory:

$$\delta_{AB} = \frac{l^2 - a^2}{4EJ} Pa + \frac{\mu Pa}{2\bar{G}A} + k \left(\frac{Pa^3}{6EJ_1} + \frac{\mu Pa}{2\bar{G}A_1} \right) \quad (3)$$

here

$$k = \frac{\frac{a^2}{3EJ_1} + \frac{a\mu}{\bar{G}A_1}}{\frac{a^2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{EJ_1} + \frac{1}{EJ_2} \right) + \mu a \left(\frac{1}{\bar{G}A_1} + \frac{1}{\bar{G}A_2} \right)} \quad (4)$$

where EJ_i and $\bar{G}A_i$ are stiffness of sub-beam for flexure and shear respectively.

Taking equation (2) and (3) into equation (1), we get

$$C = \frac{21^3 + (kK-1)a^3}{12\bar{E}\bar{J}} \left[1 + \frac{61^3 + 3kMa^3}{21^3 + (kK-1)a^3} \frac{\bar{E}\bar{J}}{\bar{C}\bar{A}a^2} \right] \quad (5)$$

where

$$K = \frac{\bar{E}\bar{J}}{\bar{E}\bar{J}_1} \quad M = \frac{\bar{C}\bar{A}}{\bar{C}\bar{A}_1} \quad (6)$$

It is needed to point out that when θ is neither 0 nor 90 degree, the bending-twist coupling will occur. Since this twist is restricted at the supporting point, the compliance will decrease. The calculated results show that the serious coupling is in the beam [O5/45]_S and its compliance decrement is less than 0.1 percent, which is neglectable. Thus, the energy release rate produced by applied load is as follows:

$$G_{II}^{(M)} = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} = \frac{a^2 P^2 (kK-1)}{8b\bar{E}\bar{J}} \left(1 + \mu \frac{kM}{kK-1} \cdot \frac{\bar{E}\bar{J}}{\bar{C}\bar{A}a^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

Second, the energy release rate produced by thermal residual stress is considered. As mentioned earlier, when working temperature differs with curing temperature, these stresses will arise. Delamination can make the residual stresses relax and the elastic energy release. Having calculated these stresses, we get this part of energy release rate:

$$G_{II}^{(T)} = \frac{\Delta T^2}{2} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{E}_i \left(\frac{N_i^{(T)}}{\bar{E}\bar{A}} - \alpha_i \right)^2 t_i - \frac{2}{j=1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_j} \bar{E}_i \left[\left(\frac{N_j^{(T)}}{\bar{E}\bar{A}_j} - \alpha_i \right)^2 t_i + \left(\frac{N_j^{(T)}}{\bar{E}\bar{A}_j} - \alpha_i \right) \left(\frac{M_j^{(T)}}{\bar{E}\bar{J}_j} \right) (z_i^2 - z_{i-1}^2) + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{M_j^{(T)}}{\bar{E}\bar{J}_j} \right) (z_i^3 - z_{i-1}^3) \right] \right\} \quad (8)$$

where, $N_j^{(T)}$ and $M_j^{(T)}$ are thermal stress resultant and moment, index j indicates the sub-beam j respectively, α_i is thermal expansion coefficient in the direction of beam axis.

Combining equation (7) and equation (8), we get the mode-II delamination fracture toughness, i.e., critical energy release rate:

$$G_{IIc} = \left[\sqrt{\frac{a^2 P_c^2 (kK-1)^4}{8b\bar{E}\bar{J}}} \left(1 + \mu \frac{kM}{kK-1} \frac{\bar{E}\bar{J}}{\bar{C}\bar{A}a^2} \right) + \sqrt{G_{II}^{(T)}} \right]^2 \quad (9)$$

where P_c is the load when crack begin to grow.

When the beam is a unidirectional laminated beam and the crack is in natural axis, formula (9) deduced to that given by Carlsson⁷:

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9a^2 P_c^2}{16Eb^2 h^3} \left(1 + \frac{\mu Eh^2}{9Ga^2} \right)$$

2. Analysis on Stability of Crack Growth.

The stability of crack growth may be judged from the sign of dG_{II}/da . From equation (8), it is obvious that $dG_{II}^{(T)}/da=0$, hence

$$\frac{dG_{II}}{da} = \frac{\sqrt{G_{II}^{(M)}} + \sqrt{G_{II}^{(T)}}}{\sqrt{G_{II}^{(M)}}} \frac{dG_{II}^{(M)}}{da}$$

The stability of crack growth is independent of $G_{II}^{(T)}$ and can be judged by $dG_{II}^{(M)}/da$ only.

Under the condition of fixed load

$$\frac{dG_{II}^{(M)}}{da} = \frac{(kK-1)aP^2}{4b\bar{E}\bar{J}} > 0 \quad (11)$$

so that the crack growth is always unstable.

Under the condition of fixed grip

$$\frac{dG_{II}^{(M)}}{da} = \frac{\delta^2}{2bC^2} \left[\frac{d^2C}{da^2} - \frac{2}{C} \left(\frac{dC}{da} \right)^2 \right] \quad (12)$$

When influence of shear is neglected, the equation (12) gives:

$$\frac{dG_{II}^{(M)}}{da} = \frac{(kK-1)a\delta^2}{4\bar{E}\bar{J}C^2} \left[1 - \frac{3(kK-1)a^3}{a^3(kK-1)+2l^3} \right] \quad (13)$$

When the crack length a meets

$$a \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{kK-1}} \quad (14)$$

the value of dG_{II}/da is positive so that the crack will grow unstably.

For the laminated beam with $m=5$, the maximum length for unstable growth is 0.5851. Taking $a=0.51$, the crack will grow unstably so that the critical load can be measured accurately.

EXPERIMENT

To make the delamination occur in small deflection stage, the specimen size is chosen as $140 \times 20 \times 3 \text{mm}^3$ in this work. It is cut from aramid/epoxy laminate $[0_5/\theta]_s^*$. The crack is cut by a knife in interface $(0/\theta)$ carefully and is made to grow along the interface to the required length under a special load condition. Colouring agent is used to seep into crack in order to measure the initial crack length accurately.

The specimen is set on a tool of three-point flexure and tested on the MTS test machine. The applied load is controlled by grip displacement and $P-\delta$ curve is drawn at same time. The crack is monitored by a microscopy.

In the test, along with increasing of displacement, the load increased linearly at beginning and no crack growth was found. When the load nearly reached the P_c , $P-\delta$ curve showed some nonlinear and the crack grew very little. As soon as the load reached P_c , the crack began to grow

* The properties of aramid/epoxy is as follows

$$E_L = 98.4 \text{GPa} \quad E_T = 12.9 \text{GPa} \quad G_{LT} = 4.79 \text{GPa} \quad \nu_{LT} = 0.32$$

$$\alpha_L = -3.6 \times 10^{-6} / \text{K} \quad \alpha_T = 54 \times 10^{-6} / \text{K}$$

with a loud crash sound, the load dropped rapidly, agreeing with analysis in the theory. The $P-\delta$ curve was drawn in Fig.2.

For the laminate with different θ , the pattern of $P-\delta$ curve is the same, but the P_c is different significantly, as shown in Fig.3. Calculated by formula(9), $G_{IIc}^{(0/\theta)}$ is listed in Table 1 and drawn in Fig.3. For the aramid/epoxy composite in this work, the fracture toughness of interface $(0/\theta)$ alternates with different θ , It reaches its maximum near 30 degree and its minimum at 90 degree.

Fig. 2 $P-\delta$ curve

Fig. 3 Variation of P_c and $G_{IIc}^{(0/\theta)}$ with θ

Table 1 Variation of $G_{IIc}^{(0/\theta)}$ with different ply-angle θ

θ°	0	15	30	60	75	90
P_c (N)	421.4	380.7	358.3	240.1	203.5	191.8
$G_{IIc}^{(0/\theta)}$ (J/m ²)	528.6	668.9	828.3	544.1	536.3	513.7
C_v (%)	12	10	8	1	14	19

CONCLUSION

(1) The mode-II delamination fracture toughness of interface $(0/\theta)$ in multi-directional laminated composite can be measured by ENF method, and calculated by formula (9).

(2) With the ENF method, the stability of crack growth is independent of test temperature. The critical crack length is a function of material and stacking sequence.

(3) This experiment shows that the mode-II delamination fracture toughness of interface (0/θ) in aramid/epoxy alters with the variation of ply-angle θ. This variation and the mechanism will be studied further.

REFERENCES

1. Sims, D.F. and H.E. Wilson, *Composites*, (7)(1973), 185.
2. Shun-lin Li, *Acta Mechanica Solida Sinica*, (4)(1984), 555.
3. Shun-lin Li and Xiao Jun, *Acta. Mechanica Solida Sinica*, 9(3)(1988). 265.
4. Willians. J.G.J. *Compo. Mater.*, 21(4)(1987), 330.
5. Similey, A.J. and R.B.Pipes, *J.Compo. Mater.*, 21(7)(1987), 670.
6. Russell, A.J. and K.N.Street, *ASTM STP876* (1985), 349.
7. Carlsson, L.A., J.W.Gillespie and R.B.Pipes, *J.Compo. Mater.*, 20(6) (1986), 594.
8. Bin-zhen Zhu, Man Shu-peng and Xiao Jun, *Acta Material Composites Sinica*, 3(4)(1986), 62.
9. Pagano, N.J. and R.B.Pipes, *Inter. J.Mech. Sci.*, 15(8)(1973), 679.